

GREEN MOBILITY IN LYNGBY

Mie Drejer, Jacob Thurnhuber and Sofie Kongsted

DTU Civil Engineering/DTU Transport, Technical University of Denmark

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The municipality of Lyngby has visions to attract more visitors and create more life in the centre of Lyngby. These visions include a densification of Lyngby, and the creating of attractive pedestrian environments in connection with the new light rail. The car traffic in the centre of Lyngby already puts a lot of pressure on the infrastructure, and it might grow, if growth continues.

Furthermore, the shop owners and the municipality fears that reductions to the accessibility for cars, could lower the income of the shops and have consequences for the trade life in general. Given the conflicting visions and concerns, a dedicated effort is required to develop balancing strategies.

The purpose of this subject is to study the different traffic- and behaviour patterns of the visitors in Lyngby, and to suggest strategies, which will focus on the improvement of the traffic problem in the centre of Lyngby. The study will cater for both the visitors and green mobility.

APPROACH

To approach the problem a study in form of a questionnaire will give an account on the customer's behaviour in the matter of transport and shopping. It will end in a thorough analysis of the parking opportunities and the overall effects of green mobility. The effects of both fewer and more expensive parking lots, better parking opportunities for bicycles and in general better circumstances for the users of green- and public transport.

Furthermore, the study will consider the new light rail and the effects it will have on Lyngby's traffic and shopping opportunities.

RESULTS

The results of the questionnaire will give a picture of how visitors/shoppers behave and what their preferences towards transport are. The results can guide future decisions, e.g. if it is possible to change the customers' behaviours with the visions about green transport, and what impact this could have on patronage and turnover. According to previous studies cyclists spent less money every time they shop, but may instead shop more often. That is why it is necessary to meet a wider customer surface and urge the customers of Lyngby to find a greener way to make their shopping.

REFERENCES

Københavns Kommune 2012, Indkøb og transportvaner I København, Center for Trafik, København.